

Horizon Europe Work Programme

BIG LEAP

Next Generation of Battery Management Systems to increase Interoperability, bridge the Gap between 1st and SL-BESS, Extend Adaptability and emPower battery value chains

D8.2 – Updated Communication, Dissemination and Clustering strategy

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Executive Summary

The BIG LEAP project aims to make second-life batteries more reliable and easier to use in the energy sector. By improving the battery management system (BMS) and developing new strategies for diagnosis and operation, the project aims to increase the use of second-life batteries in energy storage systems. The project will also develop a cloud-based system for remote maintenance and data management.

This document corresponds to D8.2 (M18) and provides a comprehensive description of the first CDC-P by month 18 (M18), scheduled for June 2025. It will outline the project's target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and roles and responsibilities. Project branding elements, including the logo, templates, social media profiles, and website. Additionally, this document describes a plan for the project clustering in order to collaborate with other EU initiatives.

Acronyms and abbreviations

BATT4EU	Co-programmed European Partnership on Batteries
BEPA	Batteries European Partnership Association
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BIGLEAP	NextGeneration of Battery Management Systems to increase Interoperability, bridge the Gap between 1st and SL-BESS, Extend Adaptability and empower battery value chains.
BMS	Battery Management System
CDC-P	Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
EC	European Commission
ESS	Energy Storage System
EV	Electric Vehicle
GP	General Public
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PM	Policy Makers
R&I	Research and innovation
RTO	Research and Technology Organization
SC	Scientific Community
SERI	State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
SLB	Second Life Battery
SOX	All the “State of …” functions that the BMS publishes to the system
SI	Software industry
TM	Trade Media
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This document corresponds to D8.2 and describes the Communication, Dissemination and Clustering strategy whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes are consequently disseminated to the appropriate target communities as well as to define the clustering synergies to be adopted in the BIG LEAP project.

1.1 Objectives of Work Package 8 (WP8)

The main objective of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Upscaling activities Work Package 8 (WP8) is to detail the different activities that will be done to ensure the project's successful dissemination across different geographies with an established growth path. It is set to achieve this with the assigned Dissemination, Communication and Clustering strategies, Stakeholders engagement activities, and Exploitation and Upscaling plan, to develop actions beyond the time of this project (TRL6/7) and reach the highest TRL9 for the interoperation of BESS in the shortest period, no later than 2027, not only in EU but also in strategic geographies such as Africa or India. This WP will also contribute, upon invitation by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions.

1.2 Objectives of Task 8.1 - Communication and Dissemination Strategy

A detailed Communication, Dissemination, and Clustering Plan (CDC-P) will be elaborated by AEMIS at the beginning of the project (M6, D8.1), based on the preliminary indications given in proposal stage and in collaboration with all the consortium partners. It will outline the project's audiences, key messages, communication channels for dissemination, and the clustering plan including roles and responsibilities. All partners will carry out CDC-P activities that will be monitored throughout the progressive updates of the CDC-P evaluated against the KPIs established.

2. Objectives of the CDC-P

The main goal of the BIG LEAP communication, dissemination and clustering strategy plan is to ensure that the project results and outputs are effectively and efficiently disseminated to guarantee their replicability. It involves the implementation of a CDC-P.

The overall objective of the CDC-P is to transfer knowledge and results to selected target audiences in the energy sector, academia as well as other monitoring experts, eventually enabling the use and uptake of the results and maximising the project's outcomes and impacts.

The CDC-P aims to present project information in a clear and accessible way, considering the European community's audience. It will cover project execution, technology follow-up, and convert scientific data into easily understandable information.

The project will implement a Communication, Dissemination, and Clustering Plan (CDC-P) WP8 guided by AEIMIS to enable the knowledge and results to be diffused among targeted audiences.

The strategy will be tailored to the battery value chain players, including Research and Technology Organization working on fields of BMS or ESS, allowing them to quickly advance in TLR levels and quickly achieve market uptake after the end of the project. The high involvement of key project partners across the international battery innovation ecosystem fosters the CDP-P's success.

The overall objective of the CDP-P is to transfer knowledge and results to selected target audiences in the energy sector, academia as well as other monitoring experts, eventually enabling the use and uptake of the results and maximising the project's outcomes and impacts.

3. Target audiences and key messages

The success of the BIG LEAP project relies heavily on effective communication and engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders. Identifying and understanding the target audiences is crucial for tailoring communication strategies to ensure maximum impact and uptake of project outcomes.

The following table shows the target groups identified within the BIG LEAP project and a short description each one of the different stakeholders:

Table 1: BIG LEAP Target Audiences.

Targeted results/content	Target group
SLB ESS Market	<p>It involves every actor or industry that could be interested in acquiring the services of an SLB.</p> <p>It is expected that BIG LEAP results will play a major role in the industries of Stationary ESS, Smart Grid Technologies, Electricity Storage from Renewables, as well as any other applications for industrial, commercial, and residential markets.</p>

Battery OEMs	<p>The transportation industry is the major producer of batteries in the world, due to its huge automobile EV production and the steady rise of E-Vessels in the maritime industry.</p> <p>The creation of additional business markets across the value chain of electric transportation will result in higher profits and cost-effective vehicles.</p> <p>In addition, this industry is forecasted to enter the SLB market by directly repurposing batteries and selling them, taking advantage of their stock.</p>
Standardization Organizations and Policy Makers	<p>The work performed in this project, no matter the final commercial results, will pave the way toward new policies and standardization practices. The results will directly feed sustainable policy initiatives at an EU level while achieving regulation in the fabrication and readaptation phases of the SLB industry, ensuring safe and effective batteries in the wide market.</p>
Energy Production Industry	<p>The outcomes of this project would help with the electrification of society in diverse industry areas. The batteries directly use energy to function, so their high involvement in society will directly impact the stakeholders dedicated to energy production by increasing its demand. Renewable energy production can be positively benefited by SL-BESS as they address their energy intermittence, the lead limiting factor of alternative energies.</p>
Battery Recyclers	<p>The results of BIG LEAP are aimed at expanding the lifetime of an EV battery through its usage in various applications. Stakeholders dedicated to the production of SL-BESS could be found themselves competing in a saturated market, especially if other industries, like the automotive, start to provide them separately. Given the presence of SL-BESS in the market, stakeholders dedicated entirely to recycling processes could face a potential delay of 10-20 years in their operations.</p>
General Public	<p>It includes those that have some interest in SL-BESS and their potential applications across industries, expanding to the EV industry and the energy market repercussions, including to its positive environmental repercussions, and diminishing in fossil fuel dependency. Hence, by some extension, contribution to the larger dissemination of the project.</p>

The BIG LEAP project aims to significantly impact various stakeholders across the battery ecosystem. For the SLB ESS market, it promises enhanced access to second life batteries, cost reductions, and improved reliability. Battery OEMs will benefit from extended revenue lifetimes and increased profitability, while standardization organizations and policymakers will gain valuable insights for new policies and regulations. The energy production industry will see increased demand due to better energy storage solutions, and battery recyclers will need to adapt to the extended lifecycle of EV batteries. Lastly, the general public will benefit from the environmental advantages and reduced fossil fuel dependency brought by the widespread adoption of SL-BESS.

Table 2: Key messages per target group.

Stakeholder	Key Messages
SLB ESS Market	<p>BIG LEAP will enhance market access to second life batteries (SL-BESS), benefiting stationary ESS, smart grid technologies, electricity storage from renewables, and other industrial, commercial, and residential markets.</p> <p>Increased supply of batteries for various applications with cost reductions and improved reliability due to accurate SoX estimation and data availability.</p>
Battery OEMs	<p>The project will extend the revenue lifetime of EV batteries, increasing their resale value and profitability.</p> <p>Facilitates the entry into the SLB market by repurposing batteries, creating additional business markets and higher profits across the electric transportation value chain.</p> <p>Benefits FL-BESS producers through cheaper battery reconfiguration, expanding their revenue streams.</p>
Standardization Organizations and Policy Makers	<p>BIG LEAP will contribute to new policies and standardization practices, supporting sustainable policy initiatives at the EU level.</p> <p>The project results will help achieve regulation in the fabrication and adaptation phases of the SLB industry, ensuring safe and effective batteries in the market.</p>
Energy Production Industry	<p>The project outcomes will support the electrification of society across various industry areas.</p> <p>SL-BESS will address energy intermittence issues in renewable energy production, benefiting stakeholders dedicated to energy production by increasing demand.</p>

Battery Recyclers	<p>BIG LEAP aims to extend the lifetime of EV batteries through their use in various applications.</p> <p>The presence of SL-BESS in the market could lead to a 10-20 year delay in recycling processes, potentially creating a saturated market for recyclers.</p>
General Public	<p>SL-BESS and their applications across industries will have positive environmental impacts by reducing fossil fuel dependency. The project will contribute to the larger dissemination of the benefits of SL-BESS, including impacts on the EV industry and energy market.</p>

Additionally, AEIMIS will keep a track on the technical project milestones to share with the relevant stakeholders the achievements carried out. Since the nature of these milestones is confidential, AEIMIS will be in contact with technical partners to ensure that no confidential information is published. Below, a list of the technical milestones identified within the BIG LEAP project:

Table 3: BIG LEAP technical milestones to be communicated

Milestone	Lead partner	Date
Project requirements, metrics, dismantling study and materials project's plan established	CORVUS	M8
Design phase finalized and improved SoX, RU1/2L developed	IKERLAN	M18
BMS Cloud-base SW Layer developed	BRING	M22
BMS' HW and low-level SW developed	VTT	M25
BMS layers integration, proof of work and BMSs EOL diagnosis for all BIG LEAP aged modules	VTT	M30
Battery Cabinet and BPU manufactured	OCTAVE	M28
BMS integration and performance validation small system level	CTAVE	M34
Technological standardization roadmap, Sustainable assessment, and Business cases finalized	SIRO	M40
Commissioning of the 2 Physical demonstrators	EDF	M42
BMS and SL-BESS enhanced capabilities demonstration and validation	EDF	M42

4. Tools, channels and KPIs

This section outlines the strategies and channels that will be employed to disseminate information, engage stakeholders, and promote the objectives and achievements of the BIG LEAP project. This part is crucial to ensure that the project's outcomes and innovations are effectively communicated to a diverse audience, including scientific communities, policymakers, stakeholders, and the general public.

These tools and channels include a variety of communication mediums, each designed to meet the preferences and interests of different target groups. For example, publishing research findings in respected scientific journals will help share technical insights within academic circles, promoting knowledge exchange and collaboration among researchers. Additionally, workshops and webinars will provide interactive forums for engaging with both scientific communities and policymakers, facilitating real-time discussions and project updates.

Furthermore, participating in conferences and events will allow the project team to present their work globally, connect with industry leaders, and stay informed about the latest advancements in the field. Meanwhile, digital platforms such as the project website, social media channels, and newsletters will play a vital role in maintaining ongoing engagement with stakeholders, sharing project updates, and enhancing the project's visibility across various online networks.

Last but not least, AEIMIS will explore different synergies and collaborations with other EU funded projects in the framework of Battery management system (BMS) and battery system design for stationary energy storage systems (ESS) to improve interoperability and facilitate the integration of second life batteries.

The accomplishment of targets for various indicators will serve as an assessment for how well the Dissemination and Communication Plan is being implemented.

Table 4: List of KPIs

Tools / channel	KPI	Information source
Project identity (Brochure, Poster, Factsheet, Presentation, Roll up).	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders.
Website	500 visits per year <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics
Social media: X and LinkedIn	X (a) Followers: < 100 poor; 100 – 200 good;> 200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn (a) Followers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2-3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics
Videos	Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	YouTube Analytics
Newsletters	At least one newsletter every six months. Subscribers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >300 excellent Opens: <15% poor; 15% – 17% good; >17% excellent	Mailchimp (newsletter service), website and social media analytics
Press releases	At least 1 per year. 50 media contacted / journalists reached.	Recording of e-mails sent, website and social media analytics.

Scientific publications	10 scientific papers will be submitted to leading journals to share the project's results with members of the academic community and industry partners.	Link to site were posted or PDF version of article
Workshops and Webinars	4 scientific dissemination workshops or webinars in collaboration with similar projects. 15-20 attendees each time	Registration list
Conferences Trade fairs	Attend 6 conferences, trade fairs, and exhibitions per year	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information

4.1 Project identity

The establishment of a project identity is crucial for effective communication and dissemination of project goals, activities, and achievements. This identity serves as a visual representation of the project's core values and objectives. This section details the development process of the BIG LEAP project's visual identity, encompassing the selection of a logo, the creation of brand guidelines, and the integration of required disclaimers.

4.2 Logo decision

To ensure a democratic choice, AEIMIS circulated a survey in M1 to the partners in order to choose the project logo in which brand guidelines would be based on.

The winning design was chosen through a Google Survey form. This selection then became the foundation for developing the brand guidelines. These guidelines encompass a cohesive color palette inspired by the project's existing visual identity, and bold typography that reflects the project's progressive spirit while maintaining readability and impact.

Figure 1: Results of the BIG LEAP logo survey.

4.3 Brand guidelines

A strong visual brand identity was conducted by AEIMIS in M1 through the development of a unique logo and style guide. This ensures consistent communication across all communication and dissemination materials. Additionally, a collection of templates has been created to maintain the same level of style within the internal and external project communication.

Figure 2: BIG LEAP Brand Guidelines

4.4 EU and SERI Disclaimer

A strong visual brand According to Article 17 of the grant agreement, the BIG LEAP project's beneficiaries have already considered the legal obligations regarding communication, dissemination, and visibility activities. This includes providing targeted information about the project and its results to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. Before engaging in any communication or dissemination activity with significant media impact, beneficiaries informed the granting authority.

Moreover, all communication activities related to the project, such as media relations, conferences, seminars, and information materials, have already acknowledged the support of the European Union and displayed the European flag emblem and funding statement. The European flag emblem has been displayed distinctively and separately, without modification, and no other visual identity or logo has been used to highlight EU support. When displayed alongside other logos, the European emblem has been equally prominent. The European emblem was extracted from the [official EU website](#).

Beneficiaries have utilized the European emblem for their obligations under this article without prior approval, in accordance with the grant agreement. However, it is noted that this does not grant them exclusive use rights. Additionally, they have refrained from appropriating the emblem or any similar trademark or logo. All communication and dissemination activities have used factually accurate information to maintain the quality of information provided.

To fulfil these obligations, a disclaimer has been included in all communication materials, stating, ***Co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement 101137815. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.***

Additionally, the Co-Funded by the European Commission logo has been prominently displayed in association with the [State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation \(SERI\)](#) logo, the Swiss federal government's specialised agency for national and international matters concerning education, research and innovation policy.

4.5 Materials

The communication materials, including a project [roll-up](#), [factsheet](#), [poster](#), [brochure](#), and [presentation](#), were developed for dissemination at conferences, exhibitions, and partner networks. They were updated after the departure of TATA power. These initial communication materials provide a foundational overview of the project, highlighting its research activities, participating organizations, and expected achievements. As the project progresses, additional materials showcasing research findings may be created.

CONSORTIUM

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BIG LEAP PROJECT

Big Leap

Dedicated to overcoming barriers in the reuse of old batteries in energy storage

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MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

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RES AFRICA FOUNDATION

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State Secretariat for Education,
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The **BIG LEAP** project is a Horizon Europe initiative that enhances operation reliability of SLB by addressing interoperability in Battery Management Systems (BMS)

Figure 3: BIG LEAP Brochure

The **BIG LEAP** project is a Horizon Europe initiative that enhances Second-Life Batteries (SLBs) by addressing interoperability in Battery Management Systems (BMS).

It develops a three-layer BMS architecture for SLBs, integrates an adaptable Energy Storage System (ESS) design, and optimizes the reconfiguration process.

Testing in physical and virtual demos aims to validate innovations, contributing to market adoption and positive impacts on the European economy through the battery value chain.

IMPACTS

The **BIG LEAP** project is a plan to make European technology more competitive by improving how batteries work in the energy sector.

-
Enhancing battery system designs for SL applications
-
Accelerating the roll-out of cheaper and qualified SL-BESS
-
Improving the sustainable pathway of Second-Life Battery reconfiguration

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 Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
 Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
 Research and Innovation SENI**

Figure 4: BIG LEAP Factsheet

Big Leap

The **BIG LEAP** project is a Horizon Europe initiative that enhances Second-Life Batteries (SLBs) by addressing interoperability in Battery Management Systems (BMS).

It develops a three-layer BMS architecture for SLBs, integrates an adaptable Energy Storage System (ESS) design, and optimizes the reconfiguration process.

Testing in physical and virtual demos aims to validate innovations, contributing to market adoption and positive impacts on the European economy through the battery value chain.

OBJECTIVES:

- We focus on designing and developing advanced Battery Management Systems (BMS) and Energy Storage Systems (ESS) with three layers that make it easy to reconfigure batteries for different applications.
- Our goal is to enhance the performance of batteries, ensuring safe and reliable operation from first-life (FL) to second-life (SL) applications. By implementing in-site End-of-Life (EoL) diagnosis and safety recalibration, we aim to extend the operational lifetime of batteries while reducing refurbishing costs.
- Our innovative Battery Management System is interoperable, adaptable, and updatable, offering three degrees of openness for swift industrial deployment.

CONSORTIUM:

Under the leadership of Brussels Research and Innovation Center for Green Technologies (BRING), BIG LEAP brings together a consortium of 16 partners from 10 EU Member States (Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Portugal, and Norway) with 2 Third countries associated with Horizon Europe (Turkey and Switzerland) and two international partners (India and Morocco).

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Research and Innovation SERI

Figure 5: BIG LEAP Poster

Big Leap

The upcoming generation of **Battery Management Systems** aims to enhance interoperability, close the gap between first-generation and Second-Life Battery Energy Storage Systems (SL-BESS), extend adaptability, and empower battery value chains.

Dedicated to overcoming barriers in the reuse of old batteries in energy storage

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Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research (AEF) / State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

Figure 6: BIG LEAP Roll Up

Figure 7: BIG LEAP Presentation

4.6 Project website

The [BIG LEAP](#) project website serves as the primary source of information for external parties, providing updates on project activities and achievements to all target audiences. It aims to keep the community and associated industries informed about project developments, while also presenting the project's achievements and novel pilot lines to the general public. The website is responsive, ensuring optimal viewing on a variety of devices and screen sizes, including smartphones.

All partners will contribute relevant project information to the website. Communication efforts by project partners and social media will be directed to the BIG LEAP website, consolidating information, and maximizing its reach.

Traffic will be further increased by establishing mutual links with partner websites, other relevant websites, and social media channels.

The project website offers:

- [Latest news](#) on project progress and results
- [Details about the project impacts, objectives, methodology](#)
- [Informative materials such as newsletters, articles, and downloadable resources](#)
- [BIG LEAP Partners](#)
- [Contact information](#)
- Social media links
- A section for newsletter subscriptions

The website adheres to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR EU 2016/679) regarding personal data protection and free movement. It includes a privacy policy, cookie policy, and legal terms to ensure compliance.

The website will feature at least one embedded YouTube video introducing the project's main goals. It will be maintained throughout the project duration and for two additional years after completion. Following this period, AEIMIS will erase all collected data unless legal obligations require longer storage.

Anonymous website traffic data will be collected and analysed using Google Analytics software. These insights will be included in project reports to understand user engagement.

www.bigleaproject.eu

Figure 8: BIG LEAP Website Home Page Mock Up

This mockup showcases the design developed for the official project website published on social media.

4.7 Social media

To reach a wider audience across different age groups, BIG LEAP will establish a social media presence on [LinkedIn](#) account and [X \(Twitter\)](#) in the first month of the project (M1). A [YouTube channel](#) was also created to host video content.

During the first project phase, social media accounts will distribute updates about the project scope and promote events showcasing BIG LEAP. This will help build an audience interested in the project's results.

Social Media platforms will be monitored to gather data on metrics, sources, content types, and followers of project messaging. This data will be used to refine communication strategies for maximum outreach and will be included in both interim and final dissemination reports.

AEIMIS, with assistance from partners, will be responsible for managing the social media profiles.

Consortium members are encouraged to follow and actively participate in the project's social media platforms. Partners should also frequently share posts on their own corporate websites and social media channels.

Figure 9: BIG LEAP Social Media Channels

4.8 Video

At least one video about the project will be produced. The scripts for these videos are drafted by AEIMIS and shared with all partners for feedback and technical validation. Once feedback is collected, AEIMIS coordinates the video production, uploads the final version to YouTube, and ensures its dissemination through the project’s social media channels and website.

The first BIG LEAP project video was created and published on the BIG LEAP YouTube channel at M15. It is available at the following [link](#).

Big Leap Project

Figure 10: BIG LEAP project presentation Youtube video

4.9 Newsletters and Press releases

Newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other BIG LEAP-related information will be distributed amongst the stakeholders every six months. These newsletters will be uploaded on the project website (in the [document tab](#)) and social media channels. Additionally, project updates could be included in the partners’ own newsletters, which are sent electronically to the stakeholders and partner networks.

[View this email layout online](#)

WHAT IS BIG LEAP?

The **BIG LEAP project** is a Horizon Europe initiative that enhances operation reliability of SLE by addressing interoperability in **Battery Management Systems (BMS)**. It develops a three-layer BMS architecture for SLEs, integrates an **Adaptable Energy Storage System (AES)** design, and aims for safe and reliable operation from H1 to H2-2030.

Leading in 9 physical and 1 virtual demo aims to validate innovations, contributing to market adoption and positive impacts on the European economy through the battery value chain.

OBJECTIVE

The overall objective of **BIG LEAP** is to enhance Second-Life battery energy storage systems (SL-BESS) applications by designing efficient 3-layered Battery Management Systems (BMS) and Energy Storage Systems (ESS), ensuring economic viability, flexibility, and industry-wide standardization.

[Learn more](#)

The **BIG LEAP** project is dedicated to overcoming barriers in the reuse of old batteries in energy storage

Latest News

The **BIG LEAP Project Kick-Off Meeting**, hosted online, brought together 31 partners on January 20, 2024. The international consortium partners from 10 European Member States and five international partners who have officially launched the **BIG LEAP** project, an ambitious 2.6 year journey, funded under the Horizon Europe Initiative. [Read more here](#)

The **BIG LEAP** project, a 2.6 year initiative will develop next-gen Battery Management Systems (BMS) that improve battery interoperability, reliability and adaptability, benefiting various applications including electric vehicles. The project aims to strengthen the battery value chain and promote a clean-energy future. [Read more here](#)

The BIG LEAP Partners

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Co-funded by the European Union

Project funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic

Co-funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic

Figure 11: First BIG LEAP Newsletter (M5)

www.bigleap.eu/news

Big Leap

General Assembly in Ninove

On July 16 and 17, 2024, the Big Leap Project held its Second General Assembly, hosted in a hybrid format by BNEF in Ninove, Belgium. This event saw participation from all project partners, who presented updates on their respective Work Packages and Tasks. [Read more.](#)

Community of Practice

The BIG LEAP's Community of Practice (CoP) is a network that brings together experts, stakeholders, and innovators from diverse sectors to collaborate on the development and optimization of second-life batteries. Through knowledge sharing, innovative practices, we aim to enhance battery management systems and accelerate the adoption of SLB technologies.

[Join the CoP](#)

Webinars

Now available the 'Battery Innovations for a Sustainable Europe: Key Insights from six Horizon Europe Projects' webinar featuring the Big Leap project and six innovative battery projects.

The future of EV Batteries

Now available the recorded workshop 'The Future of EV Batteries' by Costantino Laurenti, Big Leap Project Manager, presented an overview of the project alongside other Horizon Europe-funded initiatives, including **IMMEDIATE EU Project**, **NESTLECA project**, **TEARUP Project**, **MADEA Project**, and **PARTEBY Project**.

Interviews

As a Battery Energy Storage System operator, EDF partner in the Big Leap project, focused on the testing and validation of the newly developed innovative battery management system. For more insights, read the full interview with EDF's Emile Brun and Thomas Savel. [Read more.](#)

EDF is a leader in innovative battery technology. Specializing in testing and making BMS's operation less in understanding degradation mechanisms and developing advanced state-of-health and state-of-power models. These models are particularly designed to operate efficiently on both edge devices and cloud platforms. [Read more.](#)

Conferences and Events

The Big Leap Project was showcased at the **IEP 16th European Projects Seminar 2024**. Emile Brun, from EDF, delivered a presentation on second-life batteries. EDF is the leading provider and supplier of electricity in France and Europe. It is fully owned by the French state. EDF leads Work Package 7 at the Big Leap Project and the French demo site. [Read more.](#)

Our partner EDFN, participated in the **Energy Storage Innovation Route** held on June 4, 2024, at the University of Leoben in Austria. The event brought together key players in the energy storage industry to discuss the latest technologies, innovations, and collaborations. [Read more.](#)

WESAfrica South Africa Annual Conference: Transforming Transmission

last November 8, at Webbank CB Offices in Johannesburg.

Shaping a Future-Proof Energy System in Morocco

On October 14, the conference 'Shaping a Future-Proof Energy System in Morocco' at the Sorbet Jardin des Roses in Rabat. This event brought together government officials, private sector leaders, and international experts to discuss Morocco's ambitious renewable energy goals and its growing role as a leader in sustainable energy.

Women in Batteries

Kristina Madakovic from **Battik** represented the Big Leap Project at the **2024 Future Battery Forum** in Berlin, Germany. She actively engaged with participants from across Europe's battery industry, forging connections and exchanging insights on developments in the field. Kristina also took part in the inspiring **Women in Battery meet-up**, where she championed diversity and innovation within the sector.

Horizon Results Booster

The Big Leap project applied for the first module of the Horizon Results Booster, focusing on enhancing dissemination plans and maximizing impact. Booster is an initiative from the European Commission providing a set of services to EU-funded projects, free-of-charge, to help navigate the complexities of dissemination and exploitation.

Battery Innovations Days

Bruno Lemoine, from **BNEF**, delivered an engaging presentation on the Big Leap project during the online session titled 'From Data to Insights: Advanced Modeling and AI Innovations for Battery Modeling'. Meanwhile, **BNEF** distributed Big Leap brochures during the event in Barcelona on November 25-27. This event brought together leading policymakers, scientists, and industry experts to collaborate on shaping the future of battery research and innovation in Europe. [Read more.](#)

Follow BIG LEAP on Social Media

Co-funded by the European Union

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Figure 12: Second BIG LEAP Newsletter (M11)

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Optimising Battery Lifecycle: Watch the BIG LEAP Video

What happens to electric vehicle batteries after their first life?

The BIG LEAP project is turning that question into opportunity by developing advanced Battery Management Systems (BMS) to repurpose used lithium-ion batteries into powerful, reliable energy storage systems.

From virtual simulations to real-world testing, this short video takes you inside our mission to make battery second life safe, smart, and scalable.

Watch now to discover how BIG LEAP is driving sustainable energy innovation.

The BIG LEAP Project Celebrates One-Year Milestone

Consortium gathers in Norway to reflect on progress in battery management innovation and Second-Life BESS technologies

The BIG LEAP Project, funded by Horizon Europe, has completed its first year. The consortium met in Oslo for a two-day General Assembly hosted by **Corvus Energy** to review progress and align on next steps.

Key updates included advancements in a three-layer BMS architecture (hardware, low-level software, and cloud-based tools), as well as data-driven approaches for battery safety and second-life optimization.

Discussions covered progress on cloud-based battery models, probabilistic data methods, AI for SL-BESS, IoT cybersecurity, remote diagnostics, and flexible ESS reintegration.

A guided visit to Corvus Energy's facilities gave partners a closer look at battery innovation and second-life solutions.

BIG LEAP continues to push forward next-gen, open-source battery technologies to support Europe's energy transition.

[Read more](#)

Showcasing BIG LEAP: Advancing Second-Life Batteries in Portugal

On 6 May 2025, INEGI, one of the partners of the BIG LEAP project, took part in a national webinar hosted by the Portuguese Battery Cluster, focused on "Stationary Energy Storage: The Path Towards a Sustainable Power Grid." The event is part of a broader series dedicated to advancing Portugal's role in the energy transition.

[Learn more](#)

Interview : Exploring Siro's Role in the BIG LEAP Project

As part of the Horizon Europe BIG LEAP project, **SIRO** is playing a central role in defining and standardising the next generation of Battery Management Systems (BMS) for Second-Life Battery Energy Storage Systems (SLB-ESS). Read the interview below to learn more about their contributions to the project.

[Read the Interview](#)

BIG LEAP Community of Practice

The BIG LEAP's Community of Practice (CoP) is a network that brings together experts, stakeholders, and innovators from diverse sectors to collaborate on the development and optimization of second-life batteries. Through knowledge sharing, innovative practices, we aim to enhance battery management systems and accelerate the adoption of SLB technologies.

[Become a Member](#)

Meet our Partners

Led by BRUSSELS RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER FOR GREEN TECHNOLOGIES (BRING), the BIG LEAP project brings together 15 partners from 10 EU Member States (Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Spain, Portugal), and Norway with 2 Third countries associated with Horizon Europe (Turkey and Switzerland) and one international partners (Morocco).

[Learn more](#)

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Project funded by

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Figure 13: Third BIG LEAP Newsletter (M17)

Press releases will be released at least once a year and will announce noteworthy project advancements as they happen. With the support of the project partners, they will be written in English and distributed to the national media and the European press.

Figure 14: First BIG LEAP Press Release (M5)

Advancing Battery Innovation for a Sustainable Europe: Join the BIG LEAP Webinar

Ninove, Belgium, November 26, 2024—The global demand for sustainable energy solutions is reshaping the way we think about battery technology. Six Horizon Europe projects—**BATTERYLIFE**, **BIG LEAP**, **BATMAX**, **NEXTBAT**, **REINFORCE**, **ENERGETIC**—are at the forefront of this transformation. These initiatives are taking advancements in battery management systems (BMS) and second-life applications for used batteries, addressing challenges in sustainability and energy efficiency.

On December 2, 2024, from 10:00 to 12:30 CET, the projects will host an engaging webinar titled **'Battery Innovations for a Sustainable Europe: Key Insights from six Horizon Europe Projects,'** to share insights, developments, and strategies. This event offers an opportunity to discover the latest developments in battery technology, hear from leading experts, and explore how these initiatives are improving sustainable energy storage solutions.

The webinar will highlight innovative approaches to battery technology, including advanced methods for extending battery life, optimizing performance, and repurposing batteries for second-life applications in stationary energy storage systems (ESS). Attendees will also gain a deeper understanding of how second-life batteries are being integrated into the energy grid, reducing waste while supporting the growing demand for renewable energy. The event is designed for a diverse audience, including researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and anyone with an interest in sustainable energy solutions.

The press release will outline an engaging lineup of speakers and discussions on innovative battery technologies and sustainability projects during the event. Opening remarks will be delivered by Rocio García, moderator. The first presentation will feature Dr. Angelos Amilitis, Research & Development Director at ICCS and Coordinator of the **BATTERYLIFE** project, followed by Costantino Laureanti, Coordinator of the **BIG LEAP** project. The **NEXTBAT** project will then take center stage, presented by its coordinator Mikko Pihlatie, Research Professor at VTT. Luis Oliveira, Research Coordinator at INEGI and **REINFORCE** project leader, will discuss advancements in product life cycle intelligence and additive manufacturing. Mikko Pihlatie returns to present the **BATMAX** project and the final presentation by **ENERGETIC**, will be presented by Ahmed Samet, Research Professor at INSA Strasbourg. A Q&A session will follow every two projects. The event will conclude with closing remarks by moderator.

The webinar is free to attend and will be held online via Zoom. Registration is required to secure your spot. Visit [this link](#) for further details.

December 2, 2024, from 10:00 to 12:30 CET
[Register for free here](#)

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PROJECTS OVERVIEW

The vision of **BATTERYLIFE** is to facilitate the smooth transition of batteries to 2nd life use, boost the innovation of the European Battery industry by providing enablers to implement open adaptable smart Battery Management Systems (BMS) and improved system designs, as well as proposing methods for the efficient and reliable reconfiguration of used batteries.

The **BIG LEAP** project is a Horizon Europe initiative that enhances operation reliability of SLB by addressing interoperability in Battery Management Systems (BMS). It develops a three-layer BMS architecture for SLBs, integrates an adaptable Energy Storage System (ESS) design, and aims for safe and reliable operation from FL to SL-BESS. Testing in 2 physical and 1 virtual demo aims to validate innovations, contributing to market adoption and positive impacts on the European economy through the battery value chain. In the search for sustainable mobility and energy system transition solutions, batteries emerge as a fundamental technology for the advancement of electric cars, renewable energy storage, and the reduction of carbon emissions.

REINFORCE aims at creating a circular value chain for batteries, which promises to transform the life cycle of these products. Used, defective and unstable batteries pose new challenges along the supply chain and require new industrial processes, automated equipment, and tracking systems, as well as new strategies to prepare them for a second or third life, or even for the recycling of their components and materials.

NEXTBAT aims to develop the safest, most sustainable battery system by considering electrical, thermal, and mechanical safety. This effort includes digitalizing production, reducing the carbon footprint through recyclability, and enhancing performance with advanced battery management. **NEXTBAT** develops next-generation battery systems using beyond state of cells as well as novel architectures when it comes to module and pack designs including advanced sensing, cooling (liquid and immersion), Battery Management Systems (BMS) and safety measures by using a design by safe principles. The project also introduces innovative materials and processes to improve performance, safety, and recyclability, while working towards new industry standards for the European battery sector.

The project **BATMAX** sets out to pave the way for advanced next-generation data-based and adaptable battery management systems capable of fulfilling the needs and requirements of various mobile and stationary applications and use cases. Given the role of battery systems as a key enabling technology within the green shift in transport, mobility, and energy, it is evident that multiple combinations of requirements, use cases, duties, and businesses are placed upon battery systems.

ENERGETIC project aims to develop the next generation BMS for optimizing batteries' systems utilization in the first (transport) and the second life (stationary) in a path towards more reliable, powerful, and safer operations. **ENERGETIC** project contributes to the field of translational enhanced sensing technologies, exploiting multiple Artificial Intelligence models, supported by Edge and Cloud computing. **ENERGETIC**'s vision not only encompasses monitoring and prognosis of the remaining useful life of a Li-ion battery with a digital twin, but also encompasses diagnosis by scrutinizing the reasons for degradation through investigating the explainable AI models.

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Figure 15: Second BIG LEAP Press Release (M11)

[View this email in your browser](#)

The BIG LEAP Project Celebrates One-Year Milestone

Consortium gathers in Norway to reflect on progress in battery management innovation and Second-Life BESS technologies

Oslo, Norway – January 2025

The BIG LEAP Project, a Horizon Europe initiative focused on advancing Battery Management System (BMS) interoperability and improving the reliability of Second-Life Battery Energy Storage Systems (SL-BESS), has officially marked its first year of implementation. The project consortium came together in Norway for a two-day General Assembly to review progress, share results, and align on next steps.

Hosted by project partner Corvus Energy, the meeting featured in-depth discussions on key technical advancements, including the development of an upgraded three-layer BMS architecture (Hardware, Low-Level Software, and Cloud-Based Software) and the deployment of data-driven methodologies for improved battery safety and performance.

"This first year has laid a strong foundation for the BIG LEAP's ambition to deliver open, adaptive, and interoperable battery solutions that can reshape Europe's energy storage landscape," said Project Coordinator BRING.

Key technical milestones discussed at the General Assembly included progress on:

- Initial implementation of **Probabilistic Data Association methodologies** for chemistry adaptive self-diagnosis and recalibration.
- Development of **cloud-based digital twins**.
- Integration of **machine and deep learning algorithms** for SL-BESS optimization.
- Advancements in **IoT cybersecurity**, remote diagnostics, and big data archiving.
- Progress on **in-site diagnosis, module-level dismantling, and flexible ESS reintegration**.

The event also included a guided visit to Corvus Energy's facilities, providing insights into industrial perspectives on battery innovation and second-life applications.

The BIG LEAP Project is contributing to Europe's technological competitiveness by **pioneering next-generation battery solutions** that are safe, updatable, and interoperable, all within an open-source framework designed for circularity and long-term scalability.

[Read Latest News](#)

About BIG LEAP

The BIG LEAP project aims to **boost EU technological competitiveness by enhancing Battery Management System (BMS) interoperability** and improving the reliability of **Second-Life Battery Energy Storage Systems (SL-BESS)**. The project involves upgrading BMS architecture with three layers: Hardware, Low-Level Software, and cloud-based Software. Innovative strategies, such as Probabilistic Data Association methodology, cloud-based battery models, and advanced Machine/Deep Learning algorithms, will be implemented for optimal SL-BESS operation and safety. The BMS and SL-BESS will exhibit adaptability, updatability, and interoperability within an open-source framework, accompanied by enhanced cloud-based systems for remote maintenance, big data archives, and IoT cybersecurity. The project also addresses in-site diagnosis, module-level dismantling, and flexible-to-reintegration ESS manufacture.

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Figure 16: Third BIG LEAP Press Release (M16)

4.10 Scientific Publications

Over 10 scientific papers will be submitted to leading journals to share the project's results with members of the academic community and industry partners.

Additionally, the project will engage with at least 1 open-access repository for research data, such as [ZENODO](#), to share scientific data for open science benefits, replication, and research quality.

Likewise, the project website will compile all publications and make them available for free download.

1. First scientific paper:

A first scientific contribution from the BIG LEAP project has been accepted for presentation at the EVS38 Conference, which will take place from 15 to 18 June 2025 in Lisbon, Portugal. The abstract, titled "Dynamic Optimization of EV Charging Based on Periodically Updated Battery RUL Algorithm", was prepared by IKERLAN researchers Josu Olmos, Markel Azkue, Unai Echeverria, and Iñigo Gandiaga. This work reflects the project's technical advancements in battery management systems and predictive algorithms. The participation in EVS38, a leading global event in electric mobility, highlights the project's commitment to disseminating research outcomes to both academic and industry stakeholders. More information on the event is available at <https://evs38.org>.

4.11 Conferences and events

To meet target audiences, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community, project partners will attend 6 conferences, trade fairs, and exhibitions per year, where they will share the project's scientific results with industry and academia.

They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the local, national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events.

The following conferences and trade shows have been pointed out as being of interest to the BIG LEAP project:

Event	Location	Dates in 2025 /2026
International Congress for Battery Recycling (ICBR) 2025	Valencia, Spain	10-12 September 2025
Batteries Event 2025	Lyon, France	4-7 November 2025
Battery Experts Forum 2025	Darmstadt, Germany	11-13 November 2025
Battery Innovation Days 2025	Graz, Austria	2-3 December 2025
Battery Materials Conference 2026	Sweden	20-21 January 2026
Conference on Battery Direct Recycling 2026	Würzburg, Germany	3-5 February 2026
Giga Europe 2026	Brussels, Belgium	11-12 March 2026
Vehicle-to-Grid Conference 2026	Münster, Germany	15-16 April 2026
Power2Drive Europe Conference 2026	Munich, Germany	22-23 June 2026

Table 5: Conferences and events identified for 2025/2026

To maintain a strong project presence at dissemination events, a collaborative effort with the consortium will ensure a regularly updated list of relevant opportunities. This list shared in the [BIG LEAP SharePoint](#) will be populated with potential events, allowing partners to express their interest in participating.

Along with attending conferences and trade shows, BIG LEAP will collaborate with other initiatives under the same call to host at least 4 scientific dissemination workshops or webinars by the end of the project to address standardisation and policies, as well as four other webinars to raise awareness on the different project propositions.

5. Clustering Strategy

5.1 Related Projects Identified

The BIG LEAP project is expected to share information with projects emanating from the same topic (*Creating a digital passport to track battery materials, optimize battery performance and life, validate recycling, and promote a new business model based on data sharing (Batt4EU Partnership) HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-03*) where relevant and conform to all relevant EU standardisation requirements.

In this regard, BIG LEAP will align with the EU data strategy in the framework of granted projects under the call HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-03 to allow for availability of data, interoperable and trusted data to enhance recycling and second life application focusing on indicators and on historical data of the battery system and cells.

The BIG LEAP project aims to establish links with the results of the following topics of the Batteries Partnership:

- **Physics and data-based battery management** (HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-09)
- **Streamlined battery collection and second-life use** (HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-05)
- **Next generation technologies for High-performance and safe-by-design battery systems for transport and mobile** (HORIZON-CL5-2022-D2-01-05)
- **Research on advanced tools and technological development** (LC-SC3-ES-6-2019)

In this regard, BIG LEAP will make the link with the [project BATMAX](#) and the focus will be on sharing data both experimental and operational, and creation of adaptable physics-based models, for both physical BMS algorithms and real-time multi-scale digital twins.

BIG LEAP will also make a link with the [project REINFORCE](#) to translate standardization procedures and strategies developed on sustainability and circular business modelling into BIG LEAP project.

In addition, BIG LEAP will investigate the integration of used batteries as a second life application through both projects [TRADERES](#) and [PlAMES](#) where new electricity markets and integrated energy infrastructure using second life batteries will be analysed.

Apart from this strategy, the BIG LEAP project is actively engaging with the BMS Alliance clustering, which includes four key projects: [NEMO Project](#), [BATMAX](#), [ENERGETIC](#), and [NEXTBMS](#). Through this collaboration, BIG LEAP aims to integrate and contribute to the clustering efforts.

A [Related Initiatives](#) section was included on the project's website with the abovementioned initiatives [BATMAX](#), [BATTEREVERSE](#), [BEPA](#), [RECIRCULATE](#), [HAVEN](#), [REBELION](#), [REINFORCE](#), [TRADERES](#), [BATTERY 2030](#), [BATTERY2LIFE](#), [NEXTBAT](#) and [ENERGETIC](#).

Figure 17: BIG LEAP Related Initiatives Tab on the Website

By M18, several activities were carried out to initiate contact with potential partners for clustering opportunities. At the beginning of the project, a mapping exercise was conducted to identify relevant Horizon Europe projects with aligned objectives, as outlined in the clustering strategy documented in Deliverable D8.1, Section 5. Building on this foundation, communication was established with project coordinators and dissemination managers through personalized emails, introducing our project and proposing potential synergies. Follow-up messages were sent to maintain engagement and coordinate suitable meeting times. Internal coordination ensured that appropriate representatives were involved in the discussions, and a summary table was created to track all contacts, responses, and agreed next steps. These efforts aim to lay the groundwork for forming a collaborative and impactful project cluster.

Table 6 provides an overview of the outreach and engagement activities carried out in the first months of Task 8.2 to establish collaboration opportunities with other Horizon Europe projects as part of the clustering strategy. It documents the key contacts made, their roles and affiliations, communication timelines, and the current status of each interaction. This table will serve as a log to track progress in forming a project cluster. It also helps identify next steps and follow-up actions needed to support the ongoing coordination and potential integration of interested projects into the cluster.

Table 6: Project Clustering Engagement Overview

#	Project Name	Organisation	Role	Contact Date	Status	Notes	Next Steps
1	EXTENDED	AVESTA	Coordinator	17-02-25	Interested		To be contacted again
2	COLLABAT CLUSTER	Aarhus Universitet	Coordinator	05-03-25	Waiting for decision	COLLABAT-funded projects have concluded. The cluster is currently undergoing restructuring, and the remaining project members will define the requirements and make decisions regarding the inclusion of new members.	Contact again as it was requested.
3	REINFORCE	INEGI	Coordinator	11-03-25	Interested, waiting for decision		Contact again as it was requested.
4	BATTERY2LIFE	ICCS	Dissemination and communication manager	08-04-25	Meeting Scheduled	Joint meeting BIG LEAP and REBORN	Discuss about the formation of a cluster and Horizon Results Booster module B
5	REBORN	ICONS	Communication Manager	15-04-25	Meeting Scheduled	Joint meeting with BIG LEAP and BATTERY2LIFE	Discuss about the formation of a cluster and Horizon Results Booster module B
6	BATMAX	VTT	Coordinator	11-03-25	-		Contact again

5.2 Horizon Results Booster

The [Horizon Results Booster \(HRB\)](#) is an initiative of the European Commission which aims to bring a continual stream of innovation to the market and maximise the impact of public funded research within the EU. It steers research towards strong societal impact, concretising the value of research and innovation (R&I) activity for societal challenges.

The primary goal is to increase the impact of projects by clustering them and maximizing their potential. The HRB offers services like the Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy that focuses on creating strategies for effective dissemination and exploitation of project results. It is divided into different modules.

The Module A aims to identify and create a portfolio of R&I project results by:

- **Identifying Project Groups:** Grouping projects and identifying complementary results.
- **Clustering Results:** Grouping results into Key Exploitable Results.
- **Stakeholder Analysis:** Analyzing and prioritizing key stakeholders, providing up to 50 contacts.
- **Dissemination Recommendations:** Identifying channels and potential joint dissemination actions.

One of the main outputs is the Portfolio of Research and Innovation Results. This report includes a detailed analysis including geographical and impact relevance and identification of relevant channels for dissemination.

As part of the Clustering Plan, AEIMIS is contemplating the application of these services in order to maximise efforts and engage with a wider audience.

6. Levels of dissemination

The communication methods and media chosen will depend on the geographic scale at which our target audiences operate.

6.1 European Level – European Commission

Regular project updates, including the mid-term review, periodic meeting minutes, and revisions to this document, will be submitted to the European Commission (EC). This information will provide the EC with a comprehensive picture of the project's progress and its potential impact on future policy decisions. Additionally, it will facilitate the identification of synergies with ongoing dissemination efforts of other projects, fostering collaboration and maximizing reach.

6.2 International level – Industry, Scientific community

The outcomes will be communicated to the pertinent international organisations. Scientific knowledge can be converted into useful information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be distributed by direct mailing to specified organisations and stakeholders to increase public awareness.

For the transmission of knowledge at both the research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, and workshops at both the national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be utilised.

7. Methodology

The following internal and external communication activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of BIG LEAP are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

7.1 Internal Communication

In the consortium's organizational structure meetings, those are the following main Consortium Bodies:

- The General Assembly, which functions as the decision-making body of the consortium and meets at least twice a year.
- The Work Package Leaders Board (WPLB), serving as the monthly supervisory body for project execution, reporting to, and being accountable to the General Assembly. The WPLB oversees technical developments, coherence, and implementation of project outputs within their respective work packages.

Two times a year, consortium and technical meetings will be held, and WP collaboration will be facilitated using Microsoft Teams SharePoint and/or teleconferencing tools.

Apart from individual emails, taking advantage of the project monthly conference call, AEMIS will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the CDC-P and expedite a content curating process. As a result, the partners will be better able to communicate and report on the project while also adopting a more methodical and focused approach. Each BIG LEAP consortium partner will send a representative to this meeting.

AEMIS, with coordination support from BRING, has set up a Microsoft SharePoint space to host project materials for internal use. This includes regular updates on project development, meeting documents (agendas, minutes, and presentations), and project reports. Access to this exclusive area will require a login name and password. AEMIS is responsible for managing access and resolving major SharePoint issues.

7.2 External Communication

The consortium will make every effort to spread the word about its activities through the media, journals, conference presentations, trade shows, workshops, the Commission, and industry associations. The project's findings will be published in reports, academic publications, and articles. To encourage scientific collaboration, all public communications and scientific publications shall be made open access. The partners will send AEIMIS the text whenever a translation is required, and AEIMIS will take care of modifying the design. The CDC-P will go through three phases where the objectives and nature of the activities will shift to better adapt to BIG LEAP evolution.

8. Timeline

8.1 Phase 1: Awareness phase

In the first phase, the Awareness Phase, AEIMIS will prioritise the generation of a community of interested stakeholders and suitable channels will be prioritised. It will comprise from months 1 to 12.

8.2 Phase 2: Scientific cooperation phase

This second phase knowledge is managed for the cooperation of BIG LEAP with similar projects and initiatives and ensuring the availability of research outputs to targeted audiences. It will start in M1 and until M24.

8.3 Phase 3: Exploitation-focused phase

This phase will support the actual exploitation of project results through various routes such as marketing/research/patents/others (tangible results) or workshops and roadmaps (non-tangible results). It will start in M24 and run until M42, the end of the project.

9. Activities M1-M18

9.1 Project Identity

As described in the Tools, channels and key messages section, a visual identity for BIG LEAP was created. It included the logo of the project, and the brand guidelines (typography, colours, iconography, photography style), the disclaimers, as well as different communication materials including a project [roll-up](#), [factsheet](#), [poster](#), [brochure](#), and presentation, and templates in Word and PowerPoint. These templates have been reviewed and adapted by incorporating input and emerging needs from the partners, to ensure high levels of quality for the materials produced during the project.

These materials were produced and made available on the website of the project as soon as it was operative: <https://bigleaproject.eu/>

Figure 18: BIG LEAP Dissemination Materials

Figure 19: BIG LEAP Word Deliverable Template.

9.2 Project Website

The website <https://bigleaproject.eu/> was launched on M3 (March 2024) with essential information of the project and will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Between March 2024 (M3) and June 2025 (M18), the BIG LEAP website attracted 4.200 new users, with an average engagement time of 25 seconds. The website has achieved a broad geographic reach, with users coming primarily from the United States, the Netherlands, South Africa, Spain, Finland, Ireland, and France, reflecting successful dissemination beyond the EU.

The majority of visits (3.600 sessions) originated from direct access, while organic search and social media contributed 1.300 and 411 sessions respectively. This indicates effective direct outreach, with potential for growth in search engine visibility and social engagement. The most visited content included the interoperability section (3.700 views) and the homepage (1.600 views), confirming user interest in the project's technical components. Additionally, over 480 documents were downloaded, and 405 on-page interactions were recorded.

While user engagement with content is evident, retention rates remain low, with only a small percentage of users returning after their initial visit. To address this, the project will consider adding dynamic content and regular updates to encourage repeat engagement.

Overall, the website has served as an effective dissemination tool in the period M3-M18 of the project.

Figure 20: BIG LEAP Website Analytics Audience Overview

In addition to the main sections described in 5.2, the News section features 30 posts detailing the project's scope, the consortium partners' participation in events, and interviews. The posts are available in the [news section of the website](#).

Notably, the BIG LEAP website is hosted using verified green hosting, as recognized by the [Green Web Foundation](#), working towards a fossil-free internet by 2030.

Figure 21: BIG LEAP's Green Hosting Badge

9.3 Social Media

The [LinkedIn](#) account and the [X](#) account: were created and updated with content on a regular basis since the project's kick off.

During this period, 96 publications were shared, reaching out up to 479 followers in total, and our publications got a total of 37.507 impressions LinkedIn, as of May 31, 2025.

Both social media channels are updated at least one time per week. All the partners are tagged at the bottom of each social media publication so they can be informed about the latest project publications to react, repost, comment, or share with their profiles.

9.3 Newsletters and Press Releases

The first newsletter of BIG LEAP project was released at M5 and published on the website and social media. The stakeholder list counts with more than 70 contacts since many partners have contributed including their contacts in the battery's framework with a total opening rate registered at 24,1%

The second newsletter of BIG LEAP project was released at M11 and published on the website and social media. The stakeholder list counts with more than 80 contacts from the project partners and 42 Mailchimp subscribers with a total opening rate registered at 10%.

The third newsletter of BIG LEAP project was released at M17 and published on the website and social media. The stakeholder list counts with 167 contacts from MailChimp subscribers with a total opening rate registered at 34,4%.

The first press release was launched at the beginning of the project at M5. It was sent to more than 200 local and trade media by AEIMIS and several consortium partners share the information within their websites.

The second press release was launched at M11. It was sent to more than 250 local and trade media by AEIMIS and several consortium partners share the information within their websites.

The third press release was launched at M16. It was sent to 381 local and trade media by AEIMIS and several consortium partners share the information within their websites.

The first press release was featured in media outlets such as the [WIT News](#).

Figure 22: BIG LEAP featured in WIT NEWS

Figure 23: BIG LEAP featured on the INEGI website

9.4 Conferences and events

The BIG LEAP project has progressively increased its dissemination activity from its early stages (M2) through to M18, demonstrating a collaborative and multi-channel strategy aimed at engaging both academic and industrial stakeholders across Europe and Africa.

The first action was recorded in M2, when EDF held an internal seminar to present the project's relevance to EU R&D goals. This early internal dissemination helped set the foundation for wider engagement. By M5, the project began participating in external events, with EATON presenting the project at the Solar Conference in the Czech Republic.

In M6, the consortium had a visible presence at two significant events: the Battery Show Europe, one of the industry's flagship events, and the 3rd Scientific Meeting of Mondragon Unibertsitatea, where IKERLAN contributed a poster presentation on its research. These two actions marked the project's entry into both industry-facing and academic fora.

Dissemination activities accelerated in M9, with BRING contributing to the SiGNe 2nd Workshop, and gained momentum in M10, when the consortium engaged in a wide range of high-level international events. In that month alone, EDF participated in the Energy Storage Global Conference 2024 in Brussels, and Res4Africa contributed to three events across Africa: the Shaping a Future-Proof Energy System in Morocco conference, the Growing Renewable Energy Technologies in Namibia event, and the South Africa Annual Conference. These actions significantly boosted the project's visibility across the African continent and with institutional and business audiences alike.

M11 saw the participation of SoliTek at the Future Battery Forum, further strengthening the project's industrial dissemination footprint. Around the same time, INEGI submitted an entry to the Battery Innovation Days and a national webinar on Stationary Energy Storage in the Power Grid—both marked as under review. These actions reflect a continued effort to target thematic and strategic European platforms.

By M13 to M18, dissemination efforts became increasingly academic and research-driven. INEGI submitted papers to several prominent conferences, including IEIM (M13), ICITM (M15), and CISTI (M18), focusing on second-life battery BMS interoperability and safety. These submissions show a maturing of technical results and a shift toward scientific communication.

The reporting period closes with an important academic milestone: the acceptance of a scientific abstract by IKERLAN for the EVS38 - Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition (M18). This event marks a key opportunity for the consortium to present BIG LEAP's research contributions to a global audience of e-mobility experts.

9.5 Clustering Strategy

BIG LEAP applied to the Horizon Results Booster in month 5 (M5) and got accepted to start the module A. An analysis of common exploitable results, key stakeholders to address, and recommendations concerning possible dissemination and communication activities will be delivered after completing the first module. The main objective of the module is to consolidate and organize research results from various projects within a program group for future use and dissemination activities.

Table 6 provides an overview of the outreach and engagement activities carried out in the first months of Task 8.2 to establish collaboration opportunities with other Horizon Europe projects as part of the clustering strategy. It documents the key contacts made, their roles and affiliations, communication timelines, and the current status of each interaction. This table will serve as a log to track progress in forming a project cluster. It also helps identify next steps and follow-up actions needed to support the ongoing coordination and potential integration of interested projects into the cluster.

Table 6: Project Clustering Engagement Overview

#	Project Name	Organisation	Role	Contact Date	Status	Notes	Next Steps
1	EXTENDED	AVESTA	Coordinator	17-02-25	Interested		To be contacted again
2	COLLABAT CLUSTER	Aarhus Universitet	Coordinator	05-03-25	Waiting for decision	COLLABAT-funded projects have concluded. The cluster is currently undergoing restructuring, and the remaining project members will define the requirements and make decisions regarding the inclusion of new members.	Contact again as it was requested.
3	REINFORCE	INEGI	Coordinator	11-03-25	Interested, waiting for decision		Contact again as it was requested.
4	BATTERY2LIFE	ICCS	Dissemination and communication manager	08-04-25	Meeting Scheduled	Joint meeting BIG LEAP and REBORN	Discuss about the formation of a cluster and Horizon Results Booster module B
5	REBORN	ICONS	Communication Manager	15-04-25	Meeting Scheduled	Joint meeting with BIG LEAP and BATTERY2LIFE	Discuss about the formation of a cluster and Horizon Results Booster module B
6	BATMAX	VTT	Coordinator	11-03-25	-		Contact again

As a result of these early efforts, two Horizon Europe projects, **BATTERY2LIFE** and **REBORN**, funded under the same topic as BIG LEAP (**HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-01-04**) have formally accepted the invitation to join the cluster. Initial coordination has already begun, and the participating projects are now working together to define common objectives and explore synergies for future joint exploitation and dissemination activities.

9.6 KPI Progress Overview by M18

The table below presents the progress made on the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as of Month 18.

Tools / channel	KPI	Information source	Progress at M18	% of KPI achieved
Project identity (Brochure, Poster, Factsheet, Presentation, Roll up).	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders.	A total of 700 brochures and 700 factsheets were printed and shipped to the consortium partners at M18.	0%
Website	500 visits per year <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics	Year 1: 3.100 visitors registered from M4 to M12 Year 2: 1.100 visitors registered from M13 to M17	100%
Social media: X and LinkedIn	X (a) Followers: < 100 poor; 100 – 200 good; > 200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn (a) Followers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics	X: 58 followers X no longer provides engagement rates LinkedIn: 421 followers with a total engagement rate of 9,20%	X followers : Poor X engagement rate: NA LinkedIn followers: Excellent LinkedIn engagement rate: Excellent
Videos	Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	YouTube Analytics	Number of views: 100 views	Views: Good
Newsletters	At least one newsletter every six months.	Mailchimp (newsletter service), website and social media analytics	3 newsletters sent at M4, M11 and M17.	3 newsletters sent in 18 months. 100% KPI achieved.

	<p>Subscribers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >300 excellent</p> <p>Opens: <15% poor; 15% – 17% good; >17% excellent</p>		<p>167 MailChimp subscribers</p> <p>Newsletter 1 opening rate: 24,1%</p> <p>Newsletter 2 opening rate: 10%</p> <p>Newsletter 3 opening rate: 34,4%</p>	<p>Subscribers: Good</p> <p>Opening rates: Newsletter 1: Excellent Newsletter 2: poor Newsletter 3: Excellent</p>
Press releases	<p>At least 1 per year.</p> <p>50 media contacted / journalists reached.</p>	Recording of e-mails sent, website and social media analytics.	2 press releases sent at M4 and M16 to more than 50 contacts	100%
Scientific publications	<p>10 scientific papers will be submitted to leading journals to share the project's results with members of the academic community and industry partners.</p>	Link to site were posted or PDF version of article	1 scientific paper published	10%
Workshops and Webinars	<p>4 scientific dissemination workshops or webinars in collaboration with similar projects.</p> <p>15-20 attendees each time</p>	Registration list	1 workshop and 1 webinar organized with more than 20 attendees each	50%
Conferences Trade fairs	Attend 6 conferences, trade fairs, and exhibitions per year	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information	<p>Year 1: 10 conferences attended</p> <p>Year 2: 5 conferences attended by M18</p>	<p>Year 1: 100%</p> <p>Year 2: 100%</p>

As of M18, the BIG LEAP project demonstrates strong progress across several communication and dissemination channels with multiple KPIs reached, while a few areas require further attention such as the distribution of communication materials and the number of followers of X.

Conclusions

The conclusion of the BIG LEAP communication, dissemination, and clustering strategy plan emphasizes the successful transfer and dissemination of project knowledge and results to key audiences.

This includes stakeholders in the energy sector, academia, and monitoring experts, with the goal of enabling the use and uptake of the project's findings.

By presenting information clearly and accessibly, and focusing on the battery value chain players, the CDC-P aims to maximize the project's outcomes and impacts. The involvement of the BIG LEAP partners is crucial for achieving these goals and ensuring that the key messages are efficiently communicated to the different stakeholders.

10. References

European Commission. (2018). *Principles for GDPR*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/principles-gdpr_en

GDPR. (2020). *GDPR Guidelines and Principles*. Retrieved from <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

GDPR EU. (2018). *What is GDPR, the EU's new data protection law?* Retrieved from <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

11. Annex - Dissemination tables

The following annex presents the dissemination tables of the BIG LEAP project which are found in the project's SharePoint. This is an Excel worksheet shared with all partners to ensure everyone's collaboration towards a successful dissemination of the project results and to report any contributions made to the promotion of the BIG LEAP project.

Consortium partners are required to inform AEIMIS and provide input into the tables regarding:

- **Communication activities**, such as social media posts, press releases and web posts
- **Outreach activities**, including events, trade shows and online events
- **Scientific publications**

Timely updates and collaboration from all participants will be key to ensuring the successful dissemination of project results.

Table 7: Dissemination Tables (01-02)

Partner	Communication action	Description	Audience	Stakeholders reached	Link	Date
AEIMIS	Press Release	Kom Post on LinkedIn	All	10	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7175870646864805890/	M2
AEIMIS	LinkedIn post	Press Release Repost on LinkedIn	All	10	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173721207073030144	M3
AEIMIS	LinkedIn post	Website Launching	All	20	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7178707341997981696	M3
INEGI	Website post	Project Launching	All	5000	https://www.inegi.pt/pt/noticias/big-leap-um-salto-na-reconfiguracao-de-baterias-e-na-interoperabilidade-de-sistemas/	M2
BFH	Website post	Project Launching	All	6000	https://www.bfh.ch/en/news/news/2024/big-leap-project/	M4
RES4AFRICA	LinkedIn post	Project Launching	All	2832	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183457219005341697/	M3
RES4AFRICA	LinkedIn post	Repost RES4AFRICA	All	20000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7198683925240537088/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M6
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	All	479	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203347005056663552/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M5
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	Citizens	600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7203691733778374656/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M5
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	Citizens	600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204738291584118784/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M5
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	All	600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206997897962262532/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M6
IKERLAN	LinkedIn post	3rd Scientific Meeting of Mondragon Unibertsitatea on Battery- Based Energy Storage Systems	Research communities	4117	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mondragon-goi-eskola-politeknikoa_learningfrompeople-learningfrominnovation-activity-7209817454515003392-wtoT?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	M6
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	Industry, business partners	600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7208815895765299202/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M6

EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	Industry, business partners	600	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stredoceske-inovacni-centrum_sic-technologie-inovace-activity-7204477385889460224-g1CN?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	M6
SOLITEK	LinkedIn post	LinkedIn Newsletter	Civil society	2663	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/soliteks-solar-insider-august-edition-soliteksolar-rb84f/?trackingId=FNMI7uzd7Nl3Gh8XNT1MSw%3D%3D	M8
SOLITEK	LinkedIn post	R&D Team	Civil society	7168	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7234462260746682368/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M8
EATON	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	Civil society	1 653 331	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7221046465056362496/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M9
EDF	Website post	Project presentation	All	500	https://www.edf.fr/groupe-edf/inventer-l-avenir-de-l-energie/rd-un-savoir-faire-mondial/toutes-les-actualites-de-la-rd/revolution-dans-la-gestion-des-batteries-la-rd-a-la-pointe-de-l-innovation-avec-4-projets-europeens#:~:text=Le%20D%C3%A9partement%20C2%AB%20Laboratoire%20des%20Mat%C3%A9riels,durabilit%C3%A9%20et%20l'efficacit%C3%A9%20des	M10
CORVUS	LinkedIn post	Repost LinkedIn	All	500	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7283957794985156609/?actorCompanyId=101388312	M13
IKERLAN	LinkedIn post	Post in LinkedIn project video	All	1188	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7306246142864814080/	M15
SOLITEK	LinkedIn post	Post about the second GA meeting	All	8470	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/soliteksolar_solitek-bigleap-battery-activity-7310588477178286080-sEit?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAARrgIEBg4DerpaYyai04Oxdr5V8nwe03e8	M16
AEMIS	LinkedIn post	Post in LinkedIn project video	All	65	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aeimis-es_big-leap-project-activity-7317509446245490688-3ie1?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAARrgIEBg4DerpaYyai04Oxdr5V8nwe03e8	M16

Partner	Title	Dissemination Activity	Target	Date	Relevant link
EDF	EDF R&D EU project seminar	Internal seminar	Innovators	M2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7159282013013766144?updateEntityUrn=urn%3A%3A%3AfeedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3A%3A%3Aactivity%3A7159282013013766144%29
EATON	Solar Conference	Conference	All	M5	https://www.solarnikonference.cz/
IKERLAN	3rd Scientific Meeting of Mondragon Unibertsitatea on Battery-Based Energy Storage Systems	Conference	All	M6	3RD SCIENTIFIC MEETING OF MONDRAGON UNIBERTSITATEA ON BATTERY-BASED ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS - Conferences - Mondragon Unibertsitatea
EATON	The Battery Show Europe	Conference	All	M6	https://www.thebatteryshow.eu/en/home.html
BRING	SiGne 2nd Workshop	Workshop	All	M9	
RES4AFRICA	Shaping a Future-Proof Energy System in Morocco	Conference	All	M10	https://res4africa.org/events/2024/res4africa-to-host-high-level-conference-in-rabat-shaping-a-future-proof-energy-system-in-morocco/
EDF	Energy Storage Global Conference 2024	Conference	EU Institutions	M10	https://ease-storage.eu/easeevents/energy-storage-global-conference/
Res4AFRICA	Growing Renewable Energy Technologies in Namibia Event	Event	Industry, business partners	M10	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/res4africa_res4africa-windhoek-renewableenergy-activity-7260223326533357569-IGqD?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Res4AFRICA	South Africa Annual Conference	Conference	Industry, business partners	M10	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/res4africa_res4africa-busa-res4africa-activity-7261755807594119168-HrCP?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
INEGI	Battery Innovation Days	Event	Innovators	M11	https://bepassociation.eu/battery-innovation-days/#:~:text=Batteries%20are%20crucial%20to%20the%20enabling%20of%20technology
SoliTek	Future Battery Forum	Conference	Industry, business partners	M11	https://bigleaproject.eu/solitek-big-leap-2024-future-battery-forum/
INEGI	IEIM - Industrial Engineering and Industrial Management	Conference	Innovators	M13	https://www.ieim.org/

INEGI	ICITM - Industrial Technology and Management	Conference	Innovators	M15	https://icitm.org/
INEGI	The Role of Stationary Energy Storage in a Sustainable Power Grid	Webinar	All	M15	https://batterycluster.pt/noticias/segunda-sessao-do-webinar-armazenamento-estacionario-de-energia/
RES4AFRICA	K.E.Y. 2025 - Rimini Fiera - Res4Africa side event	Conference	All	M15	https:// en.key- expo.c om/
INEGI	CISTI (Conferência Ibérica) - Information Systems and Technologies	Conference	Innovators	M18	CISTI'2024 - 19th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies - Welcome
IKERLAN	EVS38 - 38th International Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition	Conference	All	M18	https://evs38.org/